

Neutrosophic Hybrid MCDM Framework to Evaluate the Risks of Excavation System

Ahmed Abdel-Monem¹, Ahmed Abdelhafeez²

¹ Faculty of Computers and Informatics Zagazig University, Zagazig, 11544, Egypt 4;
ahmed.abdelmon3m15@gmail.com

² Faculty of Information Systems and Computer Science, October 6th University, Cairo, 12585,
Egypt 1; aahafeez.scis@o6u.edu.eg

Corresponding author:ahmed.abdelmon3m15@gmail.com

Abstract: The building of excavations is an extremely dangerous job that incorporates a variety of different variables. It is possible to significantly lower the likelihood of an accident occurring by first accurately identifying high-risk variables and then taking appropriate preventative steps. Single-valued neutrosophic verbal sets (SVNVS) can effectively represent qualitative and vague information when used in the identification process for high-risk variables of excavation systems. In addition, the identification of high-risk elements associated with an excavation system is a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) issue. This issue may be resolved by using the multi-attribute border approximation area comparison (MABAC) technique. The MABAC method operates on the presumption that criteria are compensating. However, the identification process for high-risk variables of excavation systems may include characteristics that are not compensatory. Under conditions of single-valued neutrosophic sets, a MABAC approach is developed. The weights of the criterion are calculated using this approach, which uses the mean-squared deviation weight method. In addition to that, an illustrated example is carried out to demonstrate the process that is involved in the MABAC approach.

Keywords: Neutrosophic Sets; MCDM; MABAC; Mean Squared Deviation weight; SVNVS; Excavation System.

1. Introduction

Accidents are more likely to occur during the construction of the excavation if possible high-risk elements are not recognized and mitigated on time. One way to think of the excavation is as a sophisticated construction network for subterranean engineering[1], [2]. Due to the highly disguised nature of the construction process, the processing of construction information connected to excavation construction presents the managers of the project with a particularly difficult problem when compared to the processing of construction information linked to other civil engineering projects[3], [4]. In addition, in geotechnical

engineering, the experiences of specialists and engineers are essential, and they may give helpful references for engineering projects at various phases. This is because excavation construction is fraught with a great deal of uncertainty and fuzziness[5], [6].

To acquire correct risk levels, it is necessary to conduct an excavation risk assessment. The multivariable and nonlinear connection that exists among the variables and risk levels is the source of the majority of the challenges that are associated with this procedure[7], [8]. In the most recent decades, a large number of scholars have developed a variety of approaches to anticipate or evaluate the dangers associated with deep excavation. These methods include the fuzzy set theory as well as machine learning techniques like artificial neural networks (ANNs).

Smarandache offered the neutrosophic set for the first time from a philosophical standpoint at the beginning[9]. A neutrosophic set may be summed up using three degrees: the degree of truth membership, the degree of indeterminacy membership, and the degree of falsity membership. It generalizes the idea of classic sets, fuzzy sets, interval-valued fuzzy sets, vague sets, intuitionistic fuzzy sets, interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy sets, tautological sets, and vague intuitionistic fuzzy sets[10]–[12]. From a scientific standpoint, it is necessary to specify the neutrosophic set as well as the set-theoretic procedures. If this is not the case, then it will be difficult to use in actual scenarios[13], [14]. In light of this, Wang et al. came up with the idea of a single-valued neutrosophic set (SVNS), and they also presented the set-theoretic operators and several features associated with SVNSs[15], [16].

A novel approach has been developed, and it's called the MABAC technique. It demonstrates the basis of decision-making by using a clear calculation approach, a systematic process, and good logic in its operation. Peng and Yang utilized the MABAC to the R&D project choice technique to rate the projects and achieve the one they sought. This was accomplished by integrating the benefits of Pythagorean fuzzy sets with the MABAC[17], [18]. MABAC is a technique that was suggested by Xue et al. for the selection of materials to be used in interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy environments. However, to the best of our knowledge, the investigation of the MADM issue using the MABAC approach has not been published in the current body of scholarly literature[19]–[21]. As a result, using the MABAC approach in MADM to rank the alternatives and come up with the best one while working in a single-valued neutrosophic system is an exciting study area[22]–[24].

The main contribution in this paper is organized as follows:

- I. The identification of the risks in the excavation systems is evaluated under the single-valued neutrosophic sets.
- II. This kind of this problem has not been applied under a neutrosophic environment in previous research.
- III. The excavation criteria are computed by the mean squared deviation.
- IV. The MABAC method is extended by the single-valued neutrosophic sets to rank the risks in the excavation system.
- V. A real case study is conducted in this paper in Egypt.
- VI. This research uses the cost and profit criteria and the single-valued neutrosophic operations in the normalization process.

The organization of the structure of this work is described below. In Section 2, the MABAC approach is constructed such that it may solve the issue of identifying dangers in excavation systems. In Section 3, we look at an example that illustrates how the excavation system in Egypt worked. The last section of the paper is called Section 4.

2. The MABAC Method

In this section, a MABAC approach for evaluating excavation systems is presented. The MABAC approach is broken down into two distinct stages. Obtaining the weight vector of variables is the primary objective of the initial phase[15]. During the second step, the discrepancies between the excavation system and the appropriate border approximation region are determined and the options are ranked. Fig. 1 is a diagram that illustrates the framework of the MABAC approach. The remainder of this section will go into further depth about its specifics[25], [26].

Fig 1. The framework of the MABAC method.

Table 1. The MABAC variables.

Symbols	Description
M	Number of alternatives
n	Number of criteria

EXCSA (EXCSA ₁ , EXCSA ₂ , EXCSA ₃ ... EXCSA _m)	Alternatives
EXCSC (EXCSC ₁ , EXCSC ₂ , EXCSC ₃ ... EXCSC _n)	Criteria
DM ₁ , DM ₂ , DM ₃	Decision Makers
$w = (w_1, w_2, w_3, \dots, w_e)^T$	Weight Vector
e	Experts
DM _g (g = 1, 2, 3, e)	Decision Makers
r = 1, 2, 3 m	Alternatives
j = 1, 2, 3, n	Criteria

Obtained the decision matrix as:

$$H^g = \begin{pmatrix} H_{11}^g & H_{12}^g & \dots & H_{1n}^g \\ H_{21}^g & H_{22}^g & \dots & H_{2n}^g \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ H_{m1}^g & H_{m2}^g & \dots & H_{mn}^g \end{pmatrix},$$

Where $H_{rj}^g = (S_{rj}^g, T_{rj}^g, I_{rj}^g, F_{rj}^g)$ is a single-valued neutrosophic verbal number (SVNVN) of EXCSA_r against EXCSC_j donated by experts DM_g (g = 1, 2, 3, e)

Phase 1: Compute the weight vector of factors.

At this point in the process, the weight vector of the factors is acquired. A mean-squared deviation weight approach is used to estimate the relative importance of each criterion. The following is an explanation of the particulars of this phase.

Step 1: Compute the normalization decision matrix.

In this step, if the criterion is cost then the criterion should be normalized. The profit criteria are not normalized.

$$Nor_{rj}^g = \begin{cases} neg(H_{rj}^g) & \text{cost criteria} \\ H_{rj}^g & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \tag{1}$$

Step 2: Combined the normalization of the decision matrix.

There are many decision-makers and experts, so the normalized decision matrices should be combined into one matrix. The combined normalized decision matrix obtained by $Com = (Com_{rj})_{m \times n}$

Step 3: Compute the mean value.

In the future phases, a mean-squared deviation weight approach will be established. The mean value of all the different alternatives is used in this technique to evaluate every criterion. At this stage, the mean value of all the alternatives concerning the criteria is determined.

The mean value donated as $M(Com_j)$

Step 4: Compute the mean squatted deviation values (ϑ)

The mean squared deviation can be computed as:

$$\vartheta(Com_j) = \sqrt{\sum_{r=1}^m (d(Com_{rj} - M(Com_j)))^2} \quad (2)$$

Step 5: Compute the weight vector of all factors.

The weights of factors can be computed as:

$$w_j = \frac{\vartheta_j}{\sum_{j=1}^n \vartheta_j} \quad (3)$$

Phase 2: Rank the alternatives by the MABAC method.

Step 6: Compute the weight decision matrix.

The weight decision matrix can be computed by multiplying the weight vector of each criterion by the aggregated normalized decision matrix as:

$$WD (wd_{rj}) = w_j * Com_{rj} \quad (4)$$

Step 7: Compute the border approximation area.

The border approximation area can be computed by the MABAC method and donated as $B = (b_j)_{n \times 1}$

$$b_j = \left(\prod_{r=1}^m wd_{rj} \right)^{\frac{1}{m}} \quad (5)$$

Step 8: Compute the distance between the weighted normalized decision matrix and the border approximation area.

The distance between b_j and wd_{rj} can be computed as:

$$T = (t_{rj})_{m \times n} = \begin{cases} t(Com_{rj}, b_j) & \text{if } Com_{rj} > b_j \\ -t(Com_{rj}, b_j) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Step 9: Rank the alternatives.

The alternatives are ranked according to:

$$F_r = \sum_{j=1}^n t_{rj} \quad (7)$$

Fig 2. The hierarchy tree of criteria and alternatives.

3. Results

In this part, the MABAC approach is used to evaluate the excavation system. This section's primary objective is to explain how the MABAC should be used.

The building activity of excavation has a greater danger. Because the building of the excavation involves a variety of different aspects. An investigation into the building of an excavation in Zhuhai, China, is used as the case study. Excavation construction carried out in a risk-free way is an extremely important aspect of the construction unit.

Archaeology one hundred years ago was quite different from what it is now. Petrie used enormous teams of Egyptian excavators; nevertheless, their efforts were not acknowledged for the work that they did throughout the excavations that took place on a grander scale and at a quicker speed.

Archaeologists utilize a wide variety of techniques that allow for more exact documentation than ever before, which has resulted in digs that are more specific and concentrated than ever before. Archaeologists in Egypt oversee their digs, and there has been an increase in the number of efforts made to engage local populations in Egypt via various outreach programs. The project will make in Saqqara, Egypt. The Saqqara site is part of a sprawling necropolis at Egypt's ancient capital of Memphis that includes the famed Giza Pyramids as well as smaller pyramids at Abu Sir, Dahshur, and Abu Ruwaysh. The ruins of Memphis were designated a UNESCO World Heritage site in the 1970s.

It is necessary to establish both criteria and risk variables. For this research, five highly knowledgeable specialists in expert systems have been asked to carry out an excavation risk assessment. Fig 2. Shows the hierarchy tree between criteria and alternatives (risks). There are three experts to evaluate the criteria and alternatives. The weights vector of experts is $(1/3, 1/3, 1/3)$.

In this portion, it was mentioned that SVNVN may be used to characterize assessments. Every specialist evaluates every risk concerning every factor. The verbal aspects are taken into consideration. For instance, the first decision-makers compared EXCSA₁ to EXCSC₁ based on its verbal value. In addition, we have asked every supervisor to give the following data: (1) The extent to which the individual thinks that the evaluation is accurate. (2) The extent to which the individual believes that the evaluation is inaccurate. (3) The extent to which he does not have complete confidence in the evaluation. An SVNN can show all three of these different types of information. Let experts evaluate the criteria and alternatives to build the decision matrix. Table 2 shows the decision matrix by the e1.

Table 2. The decision matrix of e1 by the SVNvNs.

	EXCSC ₁	EXCSC ₂	EXCSC ₃	EXCSC ₄	EXCSC ₅	EXCSC ₆	EXCSC ₇
EXCSA ₁	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.9,0.1,0.1
EXCSA ₂	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.4,0.6,0.2
EXCSA ₃	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.1,0.8,0.6
EXCSA ₄	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.6,0.5,0.1
EXCSA ₅	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.8,0.1,0.1
EXCSA ₆	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.9,0.1,0.1
EXCSA ₇	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2
EXCSA ₈	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.1,0.8,0.6
EXCSA ₉	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.6,0.5,0.1
EXCSA ₁₀	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.9,0.1,0.1

Phase 1: Compute the weights vector of each criterion.

Step 1: Compute the normalization decision matrix.

In this step, we specify the cost and profit criteria to make a normalization matrix on the cost criteria only. Cost criterion is a cost criterion and others are profit criteria. The normalization decision matrix is shown in Table 3.

Table 3. The normalized decision matrix of e2 (Nor²).

	EXCSC ₁	EXCSC ₂	EXCSC ₃	EXCSC ₄	EXCSC ₅	EXCSC ₆	EXCSC ₇
EXCSA ₁	0.1,0.5,0.6	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.2,0.8,0.4
EXCSA ₂	0.4,0.2,0.2	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.4,0.6,0.2
EXCSA ₃	0.6,0.2,0.1	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.1,0.8,0.6
EXCSA ₄	0.1,0.5,0.6	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.6,0.5,0.1

EXCSA ₅	0.1,0.5,0.6	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.8,0.1,0.1
EXCSA ₆	0.4,0.2,0.2	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.2,0.8,0.4
EXCSA ₇	0.1,0.5,0.7	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2
EXCSA ₈	0.1,0.5,0.6	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1
EXCSA ₉	0.6,0.2,0.1	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.2,0.8,0.4
EXCSA ₁₀	0.1,0.5,0.6	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1

Step 2: Combined the normalization of the decision matrix.

This step shows the combined decision matrix table 4 shows the integrated decision matrix.

Table 4. The integration decision matrix.

	EXCSC ₁	EXCSC ₂	EXCSC ₃	EXCSC ₄	EXCSC ₅	EXCSC ₆	EXCSC ₇
EXCSA ₁	0.1,0.5,0.6	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.2,0.8,0.4
EXCSA ₂	0.4,0.2,0.2	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.4,0.6,0.2
EXCSA ₃	0.6,0.2,0.1	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.1,0.8,0.6
EXCSA ₄	0.1,0.5,0.6	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.6,0.5,0.1
EXCSA ₅	0.1,0.5,0.6	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.8,0.1,0.1
EXCSA ₆	0.4,0.2,0.2	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.2,0.8,0.4
EXCSA ₇	0.1,0.5,0.7	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2
EXCSA ₈	0.1,0.5,0.6	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.2,0.8,0.4	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1
EXCSA ₉	0.6,0.2,0.1	0.8,0.1,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.9,0.1,0.1	0.3,0.8,0.2	0.4,0.6,0.2	0.2,0.8,0.4
EXCSA ₁₀	0.1,0.5,0.6	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.1,0.8,0.6	0.7,0.5,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1	0.6,0.5,0.1

Step 3: Compute the mean value.

The values of the mean can be computed in this step.

Step 4: Compute the mean squatted deviation values (ϑ)

The mean squared error of each alternative against criteria computed by using Eq. (2). The results are shown in Table 5.

Table 5. The mean values mean squared deviation values to each criterion and the weight of the criteria.

	Mean values	Mean squared deviation	Weight
EXCSC ₁	0.464444	4.436222	0.139157
EXCSC ₂	0.608889	4.436222	0.144117
EXCSC ₃	0.565556	4.436222	0.146621
EXCSC ₄	0.635556	4.436222	0.14046
EXCSC ₅	0.515556	4.436222	0.143866
EXCSC ₆	0.665556	4.436222	0.143415
EXCSC ₇	0.553333	4.436222	0.142363
Sum	4.008889	4.436222	1

Step 5: Compute the weight vector of all factors.

The weights of the criteria can be computed using Eq. (2). The last column in Table 5 shows the weights of the criteria. The sum of all criteria is 1 as shown in the last row in Table 5.

Phase 2: Rank the alternatives by the MABAC method.

Step 6: Compute the weight decision matrix.

The weighted decision matrix can be computed by using Eq. (4). Table 6 shows the values of multiplying the weights of criteria by the normalization matrix.

Table 6. The weighted decision matrix.

	EXCSC ₁	EXCSC ₂	EXCSC ₃	EXCSC ₄	EXCSC ₅	EXCSC ₆	EXCSC ₇
EXCSA ₁	0.018554325 502179,0.08 3494464759 8056,0.0881 3304613535 04	0.043234984 7217352,0.1 1529329259 1294,0.0288 2332314782 35	0.029324249 8622452,0.1 0752224949 4899,0.0684 2324967857 2	0.014045985 0723839,0.1 1236788057 9071,0.0842 7591043430 34	0.057546460 9527626,0.0 8631969142 91439,0.028 7732304763 813	0.129073786 505034,0.01 4341531833 8927,0.0143 4153183389 27	0.071181686 1193207,0.0 7118168611 93207,0.033 2181201890 163
EXCSA ₂	0.032470069 6288133,0.0 5102439513 09923,0.060 3015578820 819	0.086469969 4434704,0.0 7205830786 95587,0.014 4116615739 117	0.131959124 380103,0.01 4662124931 1226,0.0146 6212493112 26	0.098321895 5066874,0.0 7022992536 19195,0.014 0459850723 839	0.047955384 1273022,0.0 9591076825 46043,0.038 3643073018 417	0.114732254 671142,0.01 4341531833 8927,0.0143 4153183389 27	0.056945348 8954566,0.0 8541802334 31849,0.028 4726744477 283
EXCSA ₃	0.064940139 2576266,0.0	0.028823323 1478235,0.1	0.058648499 7244903,0.0	0.065547930 3377916,0.0	0.105501845 080065,0.03	0.095610212 2259513,0.0	0.014236337 2238641,0.1

	3710865100 43581,0.027 8314882532 685	1529329259 1294,0.0576 4664629564 69	8797274958 67355,0.029 3242498622 452	7022992536 19195,0.032 7739651688 958	8364307301 8417,0.0191 8215365092 09	7170765916 94635,0.014 3415318338 927	1389069779 0913,0.0854 1802334318 49
EXCSA ₄	0.013915744 1266343,0.0 6957872063 31714,0.083 4944647598 056	0.091273856 6347743,0.0 5764664629 56469,0.019 2155487652 156	0.048873749 7704086,0.1 0752224949 4899,0.0293 2424986224 52	0.098321895 5066874,0.0 7022992536 19195,0.014 0459850723 839	0.038364307 3018417,0.1 0550184508 0065,0.0479 5538412730 22	0.057366127 3355708,0.0 8604919100 33562,0.028 6830636677 854	0.075927131 8606088,0.0 7592713186 06088,0.018 9817829651 522
EXCSA ₅	0.023192906 8777238,0.0 6030155788 20819,0.064 9401392576 266	0.096077743 8260782,0.0 3843109753 04313,0.019 2155487652 156	0.043986374 7933677,0.1 1729699944 8981,0.0293 2424986224 52	0.065547930 3377916,0.0 7959391541 01755,0.023 4099751206 399	0.014386615 2381907,0.1 1509292190 5525,0.0863 1969142914 39	0.028683063 6677854,0.1 1473225467 1142,0.0573 6612733557 08	0.113890697 790913,0.01 4236337223 8641,0.0142 3633722386 41
EXCSA ₆	0.074217302 0087161,0.0 2783148825 32685,0.018 5543255021 79	0.038431097 5304313,0.1 0568551820 8686,0.0480 3887191303 91	0.097747499 5408172,0.0 4887374977 04086,0.029 3242498622 452	0.112367880 579071,0.01 4045985072 3839,0.0140 4598507238 39	0.043159845 714572,0.11 5092921905 525,0.02877 3230476381 3	0.066927148 5581659,0.0 8126868039 20586,0.023 9025530564 878	0.071181686 1193207,0.0 7118168611 93207,0.033 2181201890 163
EXCSA ₇	0.018554325 502179,0.06 4940139257 6266,0.0834 9446475980 56	0.086469969 4434704,0.0 7205830786 95587,0.014 4116615739 117	0.068423249 678572,0.08 3085374609 6946,0.0244 3687488520 43	0.098321895 5066874,0.0 7022992536 19195,0.014 0459850723 839	0.105501845 080065,0.03 8364307301 8417,0.0191 8215365092 09	0.095610212 2259513,0.0 7170765916 94635,0.014 3415318338 927	0.047454457 4128805,0.1 0439980630 8337,0.0284 7267444772 83
EXCSA ₈	0.023192906 8777238,0.0 6030155788 20819,0.064 9401392576 266	0.096077743 8260782,0.0 4803887191 30391,0.028 8233231478 235	0.043986374 7933677,0.1 1729699944 8981,0.0293 2424986224 52	0.112367880 579071,0.01 4045985072 3839,0.0140 4598507238 39	0.038364307 3018417,0.1 1509292190 5525,0.0383 6430730184 17	0.114732254 671142,0.01 4341531833 8927,0.0143 4153183389 27	0.037963565 9303044,0.0 9965436056 7049,0.0616 9079463674 46
EXCSA ₉	0.064940139 2576266,0.0 3710865100 43581,0.027 8314882532 685	0.096077743 8260782,0.0 3843109753 04313,0.019 2155487652 156	0.097747499 5408172,0.0 7331062465 56129,0.014 6621249311 226	0.126413865 651455,0.01 4045985072 3839,0.0140 4598507238 39	0.043159845 714572,0.11 5092921905 525,0.02877 3230476381 3	0.057366127 3355708,0.0 8604919100 33562,0.028 6830636677 854	0.066436240 3780327,0.0 8541802334 31849,0.028 4726744477 283
EXCSA ₁₀	0.051024395 1309923,0.1 0668737163 7529,0.1113 2595301307 4	0.086469969 4434704,0.0 7205830786 95587,0.014 4116615739 117	0.068423249 678572,0.08 3085374609 6946,0.0244 3687488520 43	0.014045985 0723839,0.1 1236788057 9071,0.0842 7591043430 34	0.100706306 667335,0.07 1933076190 9533,0.0143 8661523819 07	0.086049191 0033562,0.0 7170765916 94635,0.014 3415318338 927	0.090163469 0844729,0.0 5694534889 54566,0.018 9817829651 522

Step 7: Compute the border approximation area.

The border approximation area can be computed by using Eq. (5).

Step 8: Compute the distance between the weighted normalized decision matrix and the border approximation area.

The distance between the weighted decision matrix and border approximation area can be determined by using Eq. (6). The results are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. The distance between the weighted decision matrix and border approximation area.

	EXCSC ₁	EXCSC ₂	EXCSC ₃	EXCSC ₄	EXCSC ₅	EXCSC ₆	EXCSC ₇
EXCSA ₁	0.047025	0.026686	0.041417	0.074759	0.007341	0.011038	0.018116
EXCSA ₂	0.000639	0.012274	-0.00257	0.046667	0.016932	-0.0033	0.01337
EXCSA ₃	-0.01328	0.041097	0.012093	0.032621	-0.00225	0.034941	0.056079
EXCSA ₄	0.023832	0.00747	0.021868	0.046667	0.026523	0.02538	0.01337
EXCSA ₅	0.005278	-0.00694	0.026755	0.032621	0.050501	0.054063	-0.0151
EXCSA ₆	-0.02255	0.03149	0.012093	0.004529	0.021728	0.02538	0.018116
EXCSA ₇	0.023832	0.012274	0.012093	0.046667	-0.00225	0.034941	0.022861
EXCSA ₈	0.005278	0.012274	0.026755	0.004529	0.026523	-0.0033	0.041843
EXCSA ₉	-0.01328	-0.00694	0.021868	0.018575	0.021728	0.02538	0.022861
EXCSA ₁₀	0.125881	0.012274	0.012093	0.074759	0.021728	0.02538	0.008625

Step 9: Rank the alternatives.

The sum of each row can be computed using Eq. (7). Then rank the alternatives according to the lowest value of the sum. Table 8 shows the rank of alternatives.

Table 8. The rank of alternatives.

	Sum of distance	Rank
EXCSA ₁	0.226382	9
EXCSA ₂	0.08401	1
EXCSA ₃	0.161305	7

EXCSA ₄	0.16511	8
EXCSA ₅	0.147174	5
EXCSA ₆	0.090781	3
EXCSA ₇	0.150418	6
EXCSA ₈	0.113899	4
EXCSA ₉	0.090193	2
EXCSA ₁₀	0.280739	10

4. Conclusion

In engineering practice, a built decision structure for risk analysis of an excavation system provides a useful guide for project supervisors to recognize high-risk aspects. This helps project supervisors to take appropriate measures in time to minimize the occurrence likelihood of risk accidents in the initial building phase of excavation. The method that has been proposed may be used in any other engineering project that calls for the judgments of DMs and the information tracked of variables. Additionally, the proposed framework is adaptable for use in the MCDM process. The last point is that the approach associated with MCDM modeling may be transformed into computer software, which can minimize the amount of time and effort required to gather and analyze the views from a variety of specialists.

A technique for a neutrosophic excavating system has been devised mainly for this work. SVNPNs are used inside the excavation system approach to display qualitative and ambiguous information. MABAC has been upgraded so that it can manage SVNPNs. In addition to this, the excavation system approach presents the central concept of MABAC and considers the non-compensation of requirements. In addition, to acquire criterion weights, the mean-squared deviation weight technique using SVNPNs has been devised. From the MABAC method and neutrosophic sets, alternative 2 is the best, and alternative 10 is the worst.

References

- [1] S.-S. Lin, S.-L. Shen, A. Zhou, and Y.-S. Xu, "Risk assessment and management of excavation system based on fuzzy set theory and machine learning methods," *Autom. Constr.*, vol. 122, p. 103490, 2021.
- [2] J. Seo, S. Lee, J. Kim, and S.-K. Kim, "Task planner design for an automated excavation system," *Autom. Constr.*, vol. 20, no. 7, pp. 954–966, 2011.
- [3] A. Ramezanzadeh and M. Hood, "A state-of-the-art review of mechanical rock excavation technologies," 2010.
- [4] S.-S. Lin, S.-L. Shen, N. Zhang, and A. Zhou, "An extended TODIM-based model for evaluating risks of excavation system," *Acta Geotech.*, pp. 1–17, 2022.
- [5] M. J. Chae, G. W. Lee, J. Y. Kim, J. W. Park, and M. Y. Cho, "A 3D surface modeling system for intelligent excavation system," *Autom. Constr.*, vol. 20, no. 7, pp. 808–817, 2011.

-
- [6] S.-S. Lin, S.-L. Shen, A. Zhou, and N. Zhang, "Ensemble model for risk status evaluation of excavation," *Autom. Constr.*, vol. 132, p. 103943, 2021.
- [7] C. H. Roosevelt, P. Cobb, E. Moss, B. R. Olson, and S. Ünlüsoy, "Excavation is destruction digitization: advances in archaeological practice," *J. F. Archaeol.*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 325–346, 2015.
- [8] D. Pamučar and D. Božanić, *Selection of a location for the development of multimodal logistics center: Application of single-valued neutrosophic MABAC model*. Infinite Study, 2019.
- [9] L. Xu, Y. Liu, and F. Liu, "Improved MABAC method based on single-valued neutrosophic 2-tuple linguistic sets and Frank aggregation operators for MAGDM," *Comput. Appl. Math.*, vol. 40, pp. 1–32, 2021.
- [10] M. Edmerdash and E. Rushdy, "An Efficient Framework for Drug Product Selection–DPS according to Neutrosophic BWM, MABAC, and PROMETHEE II Methods," *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.*, vol. 45, no. 1, p. 19, 2021.
- [11] B. Said *et al.*, "An Intelligent Traffic Control System Using Neutrosophic Sets, Rough sets, Graph Theory, Fuzzy Sets and its Extended Approach: A Literature Review," *Neutrosophic Sets Syst. vol. 50/2022 An Int. J. Inf. Sci. Eng.*, p. 10, 2022.
- [12] N. A. Nabeeh, A. Abdel-Monem, and A. Abdelmouty, "A novel methodology for assessment of hospital service according to BWM, MABAC, PROMETHEE II," *Neutrosophic Sets Syst.*, vol. 31, no. 1, pp. 63–79, 2020.
- [13] H. Ran, "MABAC method for multiple attribute group decision making under single-valued neutrosophic sets and applications to performance evaluation of sustainable microfinance groups lending," *PLoS One*, vol. 18, no. 1, p. e0280239, 2023.
- [14] D. Pamučar, I. Petrović, G. Ćirović, and Ž. Stević, "An extension of the MABAC and OS model using linguistic neutrosophic numbers: selection of unmanned aircraft for fighting forest fires," *Transport*, vol. 37, no. 2, pp. 73–97, 2022.
- [15] P. Ji, H. Zhang, and J. Wang, "Selecting an outsourcing provider based on the combined MABAC–ELECTRE method using single-valued neutrosophic linguistic sets," *Comput. Ind. Eng.*, vol. 120, pp. 429–441, 2018.
- [16] R. Şahin and F. Altun, "Decision making with MABAC method under probabilistic single-valued neutrosophic hesitant fuzzy environment," *J. Ambient Intell. Humans. Comput.*, vol. 11, pp. 4195–4212, 2020.
- [17] Abdullah Gamal, Nehal Nabil Mostafa, Sustainable Supplier Selection using Neutrosophic Sets and MCDM Framework, *Neutrosophic, and Information Fusion*, Vol. 1, No. 1, (2023): 27-33 (Doi: <https://doi.org/10.54216/NIF.010103>)
- [18] C. Jana and M. Pal, "Multi-criteria decision-making process based on some single-valued neutrosophic Dombi power aggregation operators," *Soft Comput.*, vol. 25, pp. 5055–5072, 2021.
- [19] I. Irvanizam and N. N. Zi, "Improved MABAC method for multicriteria group decision making with trapezoidal fuzzy neutrosophic numbers," in *Handbook of Research on Advances and Applications of Fuzzy Sets and Logic*, IGI Global, 2022, pp. 666–691.
- [20] P. Wang, J. Wang, G. Wei, C. Wei, and Y. Wei, "The multi-attributive border approximation area comparison (MABAC) for multiple attribute group decision making under 2-tuple linguistic neutrosophic environment," *Informatica*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 799–818, 2019.
- [21] N. A. Nabeeh *et al.*, "A Comparative Analysis for a Novel Hybrid Methodology using Neutrosophic theory with MCDM for Manufacture Selection," in *2022 IEEE International Conference on Fuzzy Systems (FUZZ-IEEE)*, IEEE, 2022, pp. 1–8.
- [22] X. Peng and J. Dai, "Approaches to single-valued neutrosophic MADM based on MABAC, TOPSIS and new similarity measure with score function," *Neural Comput. Appl.*, vol. 29, pp. 939–954, 2018.

-
- [23] Mahmoud Ismail, Shereen Zaki, Neutrosophic MCDM Methodology to Select Best Industrial Arc Welding Robot, *Neutrosophic and Information Fusion*, Vol. 1, No. 1, (2023): 08-16 (Doi: <https://doi.org/10.54216/NIF.010101>)
 - [24] N. Rahim, L. Abdullah, and B. Yusoff, "A border approximation area approach considering bipolar neutrosophic linguistic variable for sustainable energy selection," *Sustainability*, vol. 12, no. 10, p. 3971, 2020.
 - [25] P. Rani, A. R. Mishra, R. Krishankumar, K. S. Ravichandran, and S. Kar, "Multi-criteria food waste treatment method selection using the single-valued neutrosophic-CRITIC-MULTIMOORA framework," *Appl. Soft Comput.*, vol. 111, p. 107657, 2021.
 - [26] M. Abdel-Basset, A. Gamal, N. Moustafa, A. Abdel-Monem, and N. El-Saber, "A security-by-design decision-making model for risk management in autonomous vehicles," *IEEE Access*, vol. 9, pp. 107657–107679, 2021.

Received: August 07, 2022. Accepted: January 12, 2023